

Research papers

Dual-functionality of NiSe₂-CoSe₂ nanowires for electrochemical charge storage and efficient thermal energy conversion

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ABSTRACT

Thermo-electrochemical cell coupled with an electrochemical energy storage device creates a comprehensive harvesting system that can convert thermal energy into electrical energy and store it. Thus, the development of electrodes that demonstrate high efficiencies in electrochemical and thermoelectric properties is crucial, as they serve as the fundamental components in energy conversion and storage systems. This study presents the synthesis of NiSe₂-CoSe₂ (NCS) nanowires on activated carbon cloth (ACC) substrate, for enhanced electrochemical charge storage and ionic-thermoelectric applications. Comparative analysis demonstrates that NCS/ACC electrodes significantly outperform monometallic selenides in both electrochemical performance and thermoelectric applications. The NCS/ACC electrode revealed a maximum charge storage capacity of 112 mA hg⁻¹ at a current density of 1 A g⁻¹. Utilizing 1 M NaOH as an aqueous electrolyte, the NCS/ACC system showcases its pioneering role in thermo-electrochemical cell (TEC), opening avenues for efficient heat-to-electricity conversion. The NCS/ACC-based TEC delivered a Seebeck coefficient of -3.4 mV K⁻¹ and thermal charge storage of -1.02 J. These findings reveal the dual functionality of nickel cobalt selenides, offering promising solutions for thermal energy harvesting and storage in electrochemical systems.

1. Introduction

The escalating demand for advanced energy storage and conversion technologies has spurred significant interest in transition metal selenides (TMSs) electrodes [1–3]. TMSs demonstrate a diverse array of oxidation states and superior electronic conductivity (10⁻³ S m⁻¹) when compared to metal oxides (1 × 10⁻⁵ S m⁻¹) and sulphides (5 × 10⁻²⁸ S m⁻¹) [4]. In contrast, alternative materials such as carbon, conductive polymers, transition metal oxides, and hydroxides exhibit limitations in terms of their low capacitance, self-degradation, and inadequate rate capability and conductivity [5]. The bimetallic selenides deliver superior electrochemical charge storage performance when compared to single metals due to their lower band gap energy and higher redox activity [5]. Among TMSs, Ni–Co selenides have grabbed recent research attention owing to their remarkable electrochemical performance [6,7]. The redox properties of Ni–Co selenides are promisingly higher because of the synergistic effect derived from nickel and cobalt. For instance, NiCoSe nanosheets @graphene [8], NiCoSe nanowires [9], NiCoSe

nanorod [10], NiCoSe₂ nanoarrays [11] and CoNiSe @polypyrrole [12] based electrodes showed high electrochemical charge storage performance compared to that of the corresponding NiSe and CoSe electrodes [13]. Despite their promising electrochemical performance, Ni–Co selenides deliver elevated energy and power densities but often suffer from compromised cyclic stability and decreased capacity retention or vice-versa. Stability is frequently a critical challenge in redox electrodes, mainly arising from electrode material degradation associated with continuous insertion and extraction of charge carriers. This prolonged cycling process can induce physical deformations and delamination within the electrode matrix, ultimately compromising the structural integrity and electrochemical performance of the material. To tackle these limitations, it is essential to directly fabricate Ni–Co selenides on highly porous and conductive substrates like carbon cloth (CC). CC, with its high conductivity, large surface area, and flexibility, serves as an ideal substrate for binder-free electrodes, enabling efficient ion transport and enhancing overall electrochemical charge storage performance [14].

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Integration of Ni—Co selenides with a CC substrate forms a hybrid electrode that synergistically combines the strengths of each component, enabling improved capacity retention, enhanced stability, and significant energy density. For instance, Ling et al. reported the high energy density (30.71 Wh kg^{-1}) and superior capacity retention (87.64 % for 2000 cycles) of CC coupled with NiCo_2Se_4 for an asymmetric supercapacitor (ASC) device [14]. However, the stability of Ni—Co selenides can be further maximized through strategies such as tailoring the morphology and optimizing the material composition to enhance electrochemical performance. Thereby, in this study, we fabricated $\text{NiSe}_2\text{-CoSe}_2$ (NCS) nanowires on activated carbon cloth (ACC) substrate as an advanced electrode for electrochemical charge storage applications. Comparative experiments with monometallic selenides (NiSe_2 and CoSe_2) demonstrate superior charge storage capacity of 112 mA h g^{-1} at a current density of 1 A g^{-1} for NCS-ACC electrode. NCS/ACC has simultaneously achieved enhanced cyclic stability (85 % capacity retention for 10,000 cycles) and high specific energy (28 Wh kg^{-1}), attributed to the combined effects of $\text{NiSe}_2\text{-CoSe}_2$ nanowires coupled with ACC.

While the electrochemical properties of Ni—Co selenides have been the focus of extensive research for electrochemical charge storage applications, another promising area that merits attention is the ionic thermoelectric or thermo-electrochemical cell. Traditional Thermoelectric generators (TEGs) have been widely investigated due to their capability of power generation from thermal energy. TEGs are based on semiconductor materials that produce thermoelectric voltage through the movement of charge carriers, such as electrons or holes, in response to a thermal gradient. TEGs are limited due to low Seebeck coefficient (few hundred microvolts per Kelvin) and the presence of toxic materials (e.g. Pb, Te, etc.), restricting their widespread use in harvesting low-grade heat energy [15]. This has redirected research focus towards ionic thermoelectric or thermoelectrochemical cell (TEC), which generates voltage due to thermodiffusion of ions and thermogalvanic effects at the electrode electrolyte interface under a thermal gradient [16]. A TEC can generate large ionic thermopower due to large ionic Seebeck coefficient, which is a hundred times larger than the electronic counterpart and can reach several mV K^{-1} .

TEC feature a simple design comprising metal (Pt, Au, Ni, Cu and Zn) [17,18] or carbon-based electrodes [17] encasing a redox couple electrolyte (e.g. $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ or I^-/I_3^-) [19] and can generate potential differences in the order of 1–10 mV K^{-1} [16]. Redox electrolytes are used for TEC as they facilitate efficient charge transport through the reversible oxidation-reduction reactions, enabling substantial ion mobility in response to thermal gradients. This ionic conduction significantly enhances the electrochemical potential, ultimately improving the thermoelectric performance and ionic Seebeck coefficient of the TEC. For example, Kang et al. incorporated carbon electrodes in a redox couple electrolyte ($[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$) based thermocell that resulted in a Seebeck coefficient of 1.43 mV K^{-1} [20]. Similarly, Kim et al. employed platinum electrodes in redox couple electrolyte ($[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$), which produced a Seebeck coefficient of -1.29 mV K^{-1} [21]. Despite the promising potential of redox electrolytes, they produce highly toxic hydrogen gas under heating or acidic conditions. Also, in contrast to traditional noble metals and carbon-based materials, transition metal compounds (e.g. transition metal selenides) exhibit variable valences that facilitate dual redox reactions occurring in the electrolyte and the electrode. TMSs can offer unique advantages for enhancing the performance of TEC due to their favourable electrochemical properties and redox activity [4]. The high electrical conductivity of TMSs enables improved charge transfer kinetics, which is essential for optimizing the efficiency of thermo-voltage generation in TEC. For instance, Xinrui et al. fabricated a mixed-phase redox electrode ($\text{MoSe}_2/\text{NiSe}$ on Ni foam) in $0.4 \text{ M } [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ electrolyte for TEC for a charge storage capacity of 222 mA h g^{-1} at 4 A g^{-1} and a Seebeck coefficient of -1.69 mV K^{-1} for low-grade heat harvesting ($\Delta T = 50 \text{ K}$) [22]. Although the $\text{MoSe}_2/\text{NiSe}$ mixed-phase redox electrode

demonstrates a significant ability to store charge, it delivered a low Seebeck coefficient, which indicates poor heat conversion efficiency. Therefore, modifications to the electrode's composition or structure are necessary to enhance the Seebeck coefficient and improve heat conversion efficiency.

The current work pioneers the application of NCS/ACC electrodes in TEC utilizing 1 M NaOH aqueous electrolyte, instead of traditional redox couples, which has not been reported before. NCS/ACC electrodes deliver a Seebeck coefficient of -3.4 mV K^{-1} and a thermal charge storage -1.02 J for a thermal gradient of 10 K . In this work, the NCS/ACC electrodes exhibit dual functionality by serving as an efficient electrochemical charge storage material and a promising candidate for thermal energy conversion. Their exceptional electrochemical performance enables high charge storage capacity and enhanced cyclic stability, making them suitable in advanced charge storage applications. Simultaneously, the incorporation of NCS/ACC in TEC achieved the effective conversion of heat to electricity. This dual functionality positions NCS/ACC as a potential candidate that not only enhances charge storage systems but also contributes in efficient heat energy harvesting, leading to innovative solutions in advanced energy technology.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

The chemicals were of analytical grade purity and used without further purification. Nickel Chloride hexahydrate ($\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), Cobalt chloride hexahydrate ($\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), selenium dioxide (SeO_2), ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH), and hydrazine hydrate ($\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98% pure) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Ireland). Commercial plain carbon cloth – 1071 HCB with the thickness of 0.34 mm , pore density of 0.31 g m^{-3} , surface area of $1000 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, and electrical conductivity of 106 S m^{-1} was purchased from Fuel cell store, USA.

2.2. Surface modification of CC

The carbon cloth's hydrophobic properties are attributed to its strong carbon-carbon bonding, hindering metal adhesion. Activation of the CC breaks these bonds, enabling metal deposition and promoting a strong surface bond formation [23]. A piece of acid treated (1:1 ratio of HNO_3 and H_2SO_4) CC with the dimension of $4 \times 4 \text{ cm}^2$ was immersed into a 40 mL mixed solution containing KOH and ethanol solution (the weight ratio of KOH to CC is 1:4). Then the solution was continuously stirred for 3 h at a temperature of $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to vaporise the solvent ethanol completely. Furthermore, the KOH-treated CC was annealed at a high temperature of $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h with a temperature-ramping rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Finally, the CC was washed with 2 M HCl followed by DI water for 1 h and dried at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ overnight to obtain the activated carbon cloth (ACC). The contact angle measurement in Fig. S1 exhibits a significant shift from hydrophobic to hydrophilic properties of CC before and after KOH treatment. Following activation, the ACC surface displays enhanced hydrophilicity, facilitating improved adhesion of metal composites on the surface compared to the hydrophobic CC. The schematic representation of ACC preparation is given in Fig. S1 in the Supplementary information (SI).

2.3. Material preparation

The synthesis of $\text{NiSe}_2/\text{CoSe}_2$ nanowires on ACC (NCS/ACC) was achieved by facile one-pot hydrothermal synthesis. Typically, 0.05 M of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 g), 0.05 M of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 g) and 0.1 M SeO_2 (0.9 g) were added to 80 mL of deionized water, followed by stirring. Then 10 mL of $\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 12 mL of NH_4OH were slowly added dropwise to the homogeneous solution, while stirring for 30 min . The solution was transferred to a 100 mL Teflon-lined autoclave, and the ACC was completely immersed inside. The reaction vessel was sealed and placed

in an oven at 180 °C for 12 h. After the reaction, the autoclave was allowed to naturally cool down to room temperature. ACC was taken out of the autoclave and washed several times with acetone and deionized water. ACC was dried at room temperature and then annealed at 400 °C for 3 h to obtain the final product of NiSe₂/CoSe₂ nanowires on ACC (NCS/ACC). The synthesis of CoSe₂ on ACC (CS/ACC) and NiSe₂ on ACC (NS/ACC) follows an identical procedure, with a 1:1 M ratio of Ni to Co. The schematic diagram illustrating the overall process of electrode preparation is presented in Fig. S2. The details of material characterization, electrochemical and thermo-electrochemical measurements are given in the SI.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Morphological and compositional analysis

Fig. 1(a and b), (d and e), and (g and h) shows the SEM images of NS/ACC, CS/ACC, and NCS/ACC respectively, with modulated morphologies such as microspheres, interconnected nanosheets, and nanowires, which are uniformly grown on carbon fibres. Fig. 1(a and b) shows that after the hydrothermal reaction, the NiSe₂ microspheres are uniformly grown on the ACC. The NiSe₂ microspheres exhibits a well-ordered array structure that fully cover the fibres of ACC. The microspheres form a network with plenty of pores and uneven spaces with a size distribution

between 0.5 and 3 μm. Fig. 1(d and e) shows the well-established texture structure of the CoSe₂ nanosheets grown on the carbon fibres. Fig. 1(g and h) reveals the NiSe₂-CoSe₂ nanowire array architecture uniformly covering the skeletons of carbon fibre.

The grown nanowires mimic the densely packed bristles of a woolly caterpillar and are oriented almost vertically on the carbon fibre. The low magnification SEM images in Fig. S3 demonstrate the consistent and uniform growth of the active materials across all carbon fibres of the carbon cloth. The EDX spectra (Fig. S4) and elemental mapping in Fig. 1(c, f and i) represent the chemical composition and atomic distribution in the as-prepared samples. The EDX analysis presented in Fig. S4(a–c) quantifies the atomic weight distribution percentages of Ni, Co, Se, and Carbon (C) in NS/ACC, CS/ACC, and NCS/ACC. Notably, the ACC substrate yields a high carbon content across all the samples. In the sample NS/ACC, the atomic weight percentages of Ni and Se were determined to be 5 % and 10 %, respectively. In CS/ACC, the atomic weight percentages of Co and Se were found to be 6.6 % and 13.3 %, respectively. Additionally, in the NCS/ACC sample, the atomic weight percentages of Ni, Co and Se were quantified as 13.01 %, 16.6 %, and 25.08 %, respectively. Notably, it was observed that the concentration of selenium is approximately twice that of both nickel and cobalt in all the samples. No other impurity signal was present in the sample. This observation supports the presence NiSe₂, CoSe₂, and phases of mixed NiSe₂-CoSe₂ within the samples. These findings affirm the purity and

Fig. 1. SEM images and elemental mapping of (a–c) NS/ACC, (d–f) CS/ACC and (g–i) NCS/ACC hydrothermally synthesized at 180 °C for 12 h.

composition of elements within the NS/ACC, CS/ACC, and NCS/ACC composites.

The TEM analysis in Fig. S5 confirms the crystalline properties and microstructure of the selenide electrodes through high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) and selected-area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns. The low magnification TEM images in Fig. S5(a–c) and corresponding inset images of NS/ACC, CS/ACC, and NCS/ACC clearly show the formation of spheres, interconnected nano-sheets, and nanowires, respectively. Fig. S5(d–f) shows the HRTEM images of the selenide electrodes, wherein the d-spacings of 0.293, 0.285 and 0.24 nm are observed, corresponding to the (200) plane of NiSe₂, (101) plane of CoSe₂ and (211) plane of NiSe₂-CoSe₂ respectively. Also, the SAED patterns (Fig. S5(g and h)) clearly show the (211) and (210) planes of NiSe₂ and (110), and (101) planes of CoSe₂. Fig. S5(i) exhibits nanocrystalline characteristics with well-ordered diffraction rings, which are indexed to (101) and (211) planes of NiSe₂-CoSe₂ [24–27]. The SEM and TEM analysis reveal that the NiSe₂-CoSe₂ nanowires on ACC are grown vertically with the average length of about 3 μm and a tip diameter of ~11 nm.

Fig. 2(a) shows the XRD analysis of all the selenide samples. The broad diffraction peak at 25° and 44° in all three patterns can be indexed to the (002) and (101) planes, which indicates the crystalline phase of the ACC substrate [28]. The XRD graph for NS/ACC indicates the peaks at 30°, 33.83°, 37°, 51.2°, 55.8°, 58° and 64.5° related to (200), (210), (211), (311), (023), (321) and (400) planes of the cubic phase of NiSe₂ (JCPDS card no. 53-0449) [28]. Likewise, the XRD spectrum of the CS/ACC indexed at angles 30.5°, 34.2°, 35.9° and 63.2° are associated to planes (110), (011), (101), and (122), which shows the formation of orthorhombic phase of CoSe₂ (JCPDS card no. 88-1711) [29].

The sample NCS/ACC exhibit characteristic peaks at 29.8°, 33.4°, 36.9°, 37.9°, 51° and 55.5° which are assigned to the (200), (210), (211), (220), (311) and (023) planes of NiSe₂ and the peaks at 57° and 63.6° are assigned to (131) and (122) planes of CoSe₂ [28–30]. The sample NCS/ACC exhibits similar patterns to NiSe₂ and CoSe₂, confirming the formation of NiSe₂ and CoSe₂ on ACC. Raman analysis (Fig. 2(b)) further confirmed the existence of graphitized carbon with obvious D band and G band vibrations of carbon peaks located at 1356 and 1590 cm⁻¹, respectively [31]. The Raman peaks of NS/ACC located at 151, 170, 215 and 233 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the T_g, E_g, A_g and T_g modes of NiSe₂ cubic phase and are in good agreement with the previously reported values [32,33]. Three peaks at 177, 521 and 685 cm⁻¹ in the Raman spectra of CS/ACC correspond to the Se–Se stretching mode of CoSe₂ [29,30,34]. Furthermore, the peaks of NCS/ACC are located at 231 cm⁻¹ and 177 cm⁻¹, which is the simple superposition of NiSe₂ and CoSe₂ [35–37].

Fig. 3(a) shows the XPS survey spectra of NS/ACC, CS/ACC and NCS/ACC, which exhibit the signals of Ni, Se, Co, O, and C elements. The C element results from the ACC substrate (Fig. S7(a)), and O may originate

from the atmospheric moisture or slight oxidation of the electrode surface [38]. Notably, the XPS signal of Ni 2p appeared while that of Co 2p was absent in NS/ACC, conversely absence of Ni 2p and the presence of Co 2p are visible in CS/ACC, as shown in Fig. 3(b and c). Both the Co 2p and Ni 2p XPS signals are observed in the NCS/ACC sample. The high-resolution XPS spectra of C1s in all the prepared samples are shown in Fig. S7(a). And the high-resolution Ni 2p, Co 2p and Se 3 s XPS peaks of the samples are shown in Fig. 3(b–d). In the Ni spectrum, the peaks at 853.7 eV and 855.7 eV (in the Ni 2p_{3/2} band) are attributed to Ni²⁺. The satellite peaks at 861.2 and 864.4 eV can also be ascribed to Ni²⁺ [39,40]. The peak at 780.1 eV (in the Co 2p_{3/2} band) is attributed to Co³⁺, and the satellite peaks at 782.3, 785.9 and 788.1 eV (in the Co 2p_{3/2} band) are also observed for Co³⁺ [41,42]. The peak at 230 eV corresponds to Se 3 s and 233 eV, which is likely related to SeO₂ as shown in Fig. S7(b) [9,43]. The Fig. 3(d) shows Se 3d XPS spectra for all three samples, where the broad peak at 59 eV can be due to selenium–oxygen bonding structure, which comes from the surface oxidation state of Se species [44]. Meanwhile, the peak at 54.6 eV belongs to Se 3d_{5/2}, which confirms the selenium–metal bonding [42,45]. The XPS analysis has confirmed the presence of nickel–cobalt selenides in the NCS/ACC material, indicating their coexistence within the sample.

3.2. Electrochemical charge storage

All the synthesized electrodes (CS/ACC, NS/ACC, NCS/ACC) including ACC were subjected to a comparative cyclic voltammetry (CV) analysis at a scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹ within the potential range of 0–0.45 V, as shown in Fig. 4(a). Among all the CV profiles, NCS/ACC exhibited a relatively superior electrochemical performance with a high current and large integral area, indicating greater specific capacity of NCS/ACC than its single counterparts. The superior electrochemical performance of NCS/ACC in comparison to NS/ACC and CS/ACC can be attributed to its synergistic effect arising from the combined properties of both Ni and Co. This bimetallic selenide promotes the number of active sites available for redox reactions, resulting in improved electrochemical activity. Further, the nanowire-like morphology provides a large surface area and shortens the pathways for OH⁻ ions and electron transport during the charge storage and release processes [46]. Fig. 4 (b–d) shows the CVs of all three electrodes at different scan rates ranging from 5 to 50 mV s⁻¹. The CV curve of CS/ACC (Fig. 4(b)) shows two small pairs of reversible redox peaks due to Co^{2+/3+} and Co^{3+/4+}, which is due to Faradaic redox behaviour [47]. The proposed reaction mechanism of CS/ACC electrodes in the alkaline electrolyte is given below [48,49],

Fig. 2. (a) XRD and (b) Raman analysis of NS/ACC, CS/ACC, and NCS/ACC, respectively.

Fig. 3. (a) XPS survey spectrum and high-resolution XPS spectra of CS/ACC, NS/ACC and NCS/ACC, (b) Ni 2p, (c) Co 2p, and (d) Se 3d.

Similarly, the possible reaction mechanism of NS/ACC electrode with OH^- ions is given below [48,49].

Fig. 4(c and d) shows that the electrodes NS/ACC and NCS/ACC exhibited prominent oxidation and reduction peaks in their respective cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves, indicating their battery-type behaviour. Also, it shows the typical Faradaic redox reaction of nickel and cobalt-containing alkaline electrolytes.

As shown in Fig. 4(d), the redox peaks of NCS/ACC electrode shift towards positive or negative potential with an increase in scan rate, indicating a diffusion-controlled mechanism. Also, the oxidation peaks of NCS/ACC electrode have a positive shift at higher scan rates because the rapid diffusion of ions is hindered at the innermost active sites of the electrode. Only at a lower scan rate (Fig. S8), the diffusion of ions from the electrolyte enters almost all the effective pores of the electrode [48,49]. In Fig. 4(e, f) the current density of all the electrodes is plotted against the square root of scan rate. All the electrodes exhibited a linear relationship, which confirms diffusion-controlled Faradaic process in the charge storage mechanism in selenide electrodes.

Two distinct mechanisms, such as surface and diffusion-controlled process, govern the total electrochemical charge storage process. The surface-controlled mechanism is a capacitive process, which entails the electrochemical adsorption and desorption of ions at the interface of the electrode and electrolyte (capacitive behaviour), as well as surface Faradaic redox reactions (pseudocapacitive behaviour) [50]. Whereas the diffusion-controlled process involves cation intercalation within the

electrode material and ion diffusion within the electrolyte, which is often referred to as the battery-type mechanism [51]. The following equation gives a relationship between the current generated in the electrodes and the steady scan rate, which effectively classifies the contributions of these mechanisms [52],

$$i = av^b \quad (6)$$

where i is the current (mA), v is the scan rate (mV s^{-1}), and a and b are constants.

The value of b is equal to 0.5 and 1 in case of diffusion and surface-controlled process, respectively [53]. Fig. S9 shows the slopes (related to b value) of all the fabricated selenide electrodes, and the calculated b value of NCS/ACC is 0.58. This number is close to 0.5 and strengthens the claim of a reversible battery-type charge storage mechanism. The contributions of capacitive behaviour (k_1v) and diffusion behaviour ($k_2v^{1/2}$) can be estimated by analysing the current response obtained from the cyclic voltammetry (CV) curve at a designated voltage. This relationship can be expressed mathematically using the following equation [54]:

$$i(V) = k_1v + k_2v^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where I is the measured current (mA) at a constant applied potential (V), v is the ramping scan rate (mV s^{-1}), and k_1 and k_2 denote the capacitive and diffusion-controlled effects [55,56]. Fig. S10(a) shows the percentage of diffusion and capacitive contribution and S10(b) shows the contributions of two different charge storage mechanisms in the CV curve at a 10 mV s^{-1} scan rate. Hence, it can be confirmed that the NCS/ACC is primarily governed by battery-type characteristics or a diffusion-controlled mechanism.

Further, GCD analysis was carried out to examine the

Fig. 4. (a) Comparative CV plots of all the electrodes at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} . CV curves of the (b) CS/ACC, (c) NS/ACC, and (d) NCS/ACC at various scan rates from 5 to 50 mV s^{-1} . Relationship between (e) anodic and (f) cathodic peak currents as a function of square root of scan rate. In all cases, the R^2 linear fit is close to 0.99.

electrochemical charge storage performance of the prepared selenide electrodes, followed by the specific capacity calculation using Eq. (8). Fig. 5(a) shows the GCD curves of the electrodes at a current density of 1 A g^{-1} in the potential range of 0–0.45 V. Fig. 5(c–d) depicts GCD curves of NS/ACC and NCS/ACC electrodes have clear charge-discharge plateaus that correspond to the redox peaks observed in the CV curves. These plateaus are caused by the interaction between the OH^- ions in the electrolyte and the electrode material [44]. Fig. 5(b) shows the GCD curve of CS/ACC, which did not show typical Faradaic behaviour [44,57]. As shown in Fig. 5(d) NCS/ACC electrode has the longest discharging time at a current density of 1 mA g^{-1} , indicating the strongest charge storage characteristic.

In a three-electrode system, the specific charge storage capacity (mAh g^{-1}) can be calculated by the following Eq. (8) [58,59]:

$$C_s = \frac{I \times t}{3.6 \times m} \quad (8)$$

where I denote the discharge current (mA), t is the discharge time (s), and m is the mass of the active material (mg).

Similarly, the specific capacitance (F g^{-1}) in the three-electrode system can be determined using Eq. (9):

$$C_s = \frac{I \times t}{m \times V} \quad (9)$$

where I is the current (mA), t is the discharge time (s), m is the mass loading of active material (mg), and V is the cell voltage. The NCS/ACC electrode shows a charge storage capacity of 112 mAh g^{-1} (893 F g^{-1}) at a current density of 1 A g^{-1} , which decreases to 89 mAh g^{-1} (713 F g^{-1}) at a current density of 10 A g^{-1} . The NCS/ACC electrode shows superior

Fig. 5. (a) Comparative GCD profile CS/ACC, NS/ACC and NCS/ACC electrodes at 1 mA g⁻¹. GCD profile of the (b) CS/ACC, (c) NS/ACC and (d) NCS/ACC at various current densities from 1 to 8 mA g⁻¹. (e) Comparing the specific capacities of the electrodes at various current densities. (f) Comparative Nyquist plots of all the electrodes at a frequency range of 5 mHz to 70 kHz.

electrochemical performance compared to CS/ACC (73 F g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹) and NS/ACC (277 F g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹) electrodes. The enhanced electrochemical activity of NCS/ACC seems to originate from the combined redox reaction of NiSe₂ and CoSe₂, in addition to the nanowire morphology that attributes many active sites for the intercalation of OH⁻ ions on the electrode surface [27,60]. Fig. 5(e) shows the comparison of specific capacities as a function of the current densities of all the selenide electrodes. CS/ACC and NS/ACC electrodes showed a rapid decrease in the specific capacity for the increased current density and resulted in lower rate capability retention of 44 % and 58 %, respectively. Single metal selenides typically exhibit limited electronic conductivity and restricted ionic diffusion pathways due to lower charge carrier mobilities. This limits their electrochemical performance, particularly in charge storage applications, as efficient charge transport is essential for high-capacity and high-rate capabilities. The synergistic electrochemical performance of Ni and Co in NCS/ACC results in

enhanced charge storage capability due to the complementary effects of the two metals. Ni contributes to increased high specific capacitance, while Co enhances structural stability and facilitates ion transport. This combination allows for improved electrochemical performance in energy storage applications, which is evident from Figs. 4(a) and 5(a). Hence, NCS/ACC benefits from a bimetallic structure and revealed significantly a higher specific capacity at 1 A g⁻¹ and higher rate capability retention (79 %). This confirms the importance of NCS/ACC composite electrodes in achieving the synergistic enhancement of charge storage performance.

EIS analysis was carried out to evaluate the conductivity behaviour and charge transfer kinetics of the electrodes. The Nyquist plots shown in Fig. 5(f) exhibit semi-circular arcs in the high-frequency region and a linear tail in the low-frequency region for all the electrodes. The x-intercept in the high-frequency region corresponds to the total solution resistance (R_s) of the cells, which includes the ohmic resistance of the

electrolyte, the electronic resistance of the active materials, and the contact resistance between the electrode and the current collector [61]. The diameter of the semi-circular arc gives the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}). The inset within Fig. 5(f) presents the equivalent circuit model consisting of R_s (R1), R_{ct} (R2), specific capacitance resulting from double layer formation (C1) and Faradaic redox reaction (C2), along with the Warburg impedance (W) utilized for estimating the diffusion of ions towards the electroactive surface [62]. The R_s values of NS/ACC, CS/ACC and NCS/ACC are 3.2, 3.7 and 3.8 Ω , respectively. The R_{ct} values for the NS/ACC, CS/ACC and NCS/ACC electrodes are 0.34, 2.1 and 3.6 Ω , respectively. The R_{ct} value for the NCS/ACC electrode is slightly elevated compared to both the NS/ACC and CS/ACC electrodes. This increase in charge transfer resistance can be attributed to the multiphase coexistence of NiSe₂ and CoSe₂, which introduces additional interface barriers. These barriers arise from disparities in electronic properties and interfacial interactions between the distinct phases, consequently resulting in heightened resistance to charge transfer processes. This finding aligns with previous studies by Xia et al. and Zheng et al., who reported R_{ct} values of 9.46 Ω and 20.1 Ω , respectively, for NiSe₂/CoSe₂ electrodes [63,64]. Also, the R_{ct} value obtained for our NCS/ACC electrodes is significantly improved (3.6 Ω), indicating enhanced charge transfer characteristics compared to the recently reported values [63,64]. Although the R_s value of the NCS/ACC electrode is close to that of the other two selenium electrodes, the lower transfer resistance may be related to the dense nanowire structure. The overall outcomes of the EIS showcase the enhanced electrical conductivity and proficient charge transfer by the NS/ACC, CS/ACC and NCS/ACC electrodes.

The capacity retention of CS/ACC, NS/ACC and NCS/ACC are 83 %, 50 % and 98 %, respectively, for 600 charge-discharge cycles, as shown in Fig. S11. It is obvious that NCS/ACC retained the initial specific capacity after 600 cycles and surpassed the stability of CS/ACC and NS/ACC. NCS/ACC shows superiority over the other electrodes not only in terms of electrochemical charge storage performance but also in the aspect of rate capability.

Due to its superior electrochemical performance, the NCS/ACC electrode was used to develop an asymmetric supercapacitor (ASC). Activated carbon (AC) and NCS/ACC were used as the negative and positive electrodes, respectively. The ASC was assembled in the PAT-core cell with 100 μ l of 1 M NaOH electrolyte with a celgard separator between NCS/ACC (anode) and activated carbon (cathode). Fig. S12(a) shows the CV curves of ACC and NCS/ACC with potential windows of -0.8 to 0.4 and -0.2 to 0.65 at 10 mV s⁻¹, respectively. Fig. S12(b) shows the CV curves of the assembled ASC at various scan rates, which exhibit hybrid capacitor behaviour due to synergistic contributions of the electric double layer (EDL) of the activated carbon and redox reaction of NCS/ACC [60]. The GCD curves at various current densities from 1 to 10 A g⁻¹ are shown in Fig. S12(c). The maximum specific capacity calculated from the GCD curve is 34 mAh g⁻¹ (75 F g⁻¹) at a current density of 1 A g⁻¹ (Fig. S13). The Nyquist plot obtained from EIS in Fig. S12(d) reveals low R_s and R_{ct} values of 1.08 Ω and 14.92 Ω , respectively, which lead to the excellent electrochemical performance of NCS/ACC//AC ASC.

Fig. S14(a) represents the cycling performance of the assembled ASC where the device exhibits an excellent capacity retention of 85 % even after 10,000 stable charge-discharge cycles at a low current density of 2.5 A g⁻¹. The distinctive mesoporous one-dimensional structure and large surface area of the NCS/ACC nanowires offer a shortened diffusion path for the transport of electrons and ions between the electrode and electrolyte interface, thereby enhancing redox kinetics. As illustrated in Fig. S14(a), there is an initial loss of capacitance attributed to the multiphase nature of the NiSe₂ and CoSe₂ components. Nevertheless, once the structure stabilizes, it enhances the rate capability, leading to more efficient charge storage in subsequent cycles [63,64]. Overall, the NCS/ACC//AC ASC exhibits an excellent electrochemical performance and shows significant reversibility and stability.

The specific energy (S_E) and specific power (S_P) of the ASC can be

calculated using the following equations [65,66],

$$S_E = \frac{C_s \times V^2}{2 \times 3.6} \text{ Wh kg}^{-1} \quad (10)$$

$$S_P = \frac{S_E \times 3600}{\Delta t} \text{ W kg}^{-1} \quad (11)$$

Fig. S14(b) shows the Ragone plot, which compares the specific energy as a function of the specific power of our NCS/ACC//AC-based ASC with previously reported devices. The NCS/ACC//AC ASC yields a S_E of 28 Wh kg⁻¹ at a S_P of 646 W kg⁻¹, which is comparatively higher than the previously reported ASC devices based on Ni and Co selenides, as shown in Table S1. Compared to other NiSe and CoSe-based ASC, NCS/ACC//AC ASC also exhibit excellent cyclic stability (85 % capacity retention after 10,000 cycles), confirming improved electrochemical charge storage performance.

3.3. Thermochemical cell

3.3.1. Isothermal characterization

To explore the roles of redox reactions and ion diffusion in the ionic thermoelectric process, a series of temperature coefficient measurements was performed using a three-electrode setup. These temperature coefficient (TC) measurements were carried out across a temperature range from 25 to 60 °C, employing a three-electrode isothermal characterization method. This method helps to understand the change in single electrode potential resulting from a uniform temperature increase [67]. Fig. S15 shows the open circuit voltage (OCV) as a function of temperature for different systems. In each system, working and counter electrodes are identical (selenide electrodes), the reference Ag/AgCl was employed, and the electrolyte was 1 M NaOH. All the systems show decreasing OCV with increasing temperatures, indicating negative TC as illustrated in Fig. S15(a-d). The TC values are obtained by fitting the equilibrium state OCV against temperature, and the values are given in Table S2. The obtained TC values exhibit variation for different electrodes within the same electrolyte, suggesting that the entropy contributions from the electrode materials are likely to have a major impact on the isothermal reaction [68]. The negative TC values between -0.7 to -3 mV K⁻¹ for all the systems are consistent with previous reports [69,70]. In ACC-based isothermal characterization, a TC of -0.73 mV K⁻¹ was delivered because of the thermodiffusion of electrolyte ions [67]. In comparison to ACC, CS/ACC, NS/ACC, and NCS/ACC exhibited a higher TC due to their inherent redox characteristics, which facilitate enhanced electronic contribution or thermogalvanic effects [67]. The thermodiffusion contributions of CS/ACC, NS/ACC and NCS/ACC are 73, 34.4 and 24.3 %, respectively. And the thermogalvanic contributions of CS/ACC, NS/ACC and NCS/ACC are 27, 65.5 and 75.6 %, respectively. This isothermal analysis provides critical understanding of thermodiffusion and thermogalvanic contribution of selenide electrodes whose OCV changes for an increase in temperature. All these findings reveal that the redox type electrodes can exhibit ultrafast response to heat/electricity signals.

3.3.2. Non-isothermal characterization

Due to the enhanced electrochemical properties and comparatively higher TC value, the selenide electrodes are further extended to symmetric non-isothermal measurements in H-cell configuration as shown in Fig. 6(a). This study enables a better understanding of ion diffusion mechanisms involved in heat to current conversion. Two NCS/ACC electrodes are inserted into the two chambers of the H-Cell, each equipped with thermocouples to accurately measure the OCV (ΔV) and temperature. One chamber is placed on a hot plate while the other is placed on a cold-water bath to generate a temperature gradient (ΔT) between the two electrodes. A Celgard separator is interposed between the two chambers to prevent mixing of 1 M NaOH electrolyte and to facilitate ion transport. A temperature gradient ranging from 0 to 10 K

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of (a) H-type TEC and (b) sandwich type TEC.

was maintained between the hot and cold electrodes, and the resulting change in open circuit voltage (ΔV) of three different systems was subsequently recorded. Also, it can be observed that the ionic Seebeck effect has led to the movement of ions in response to a temperature gradient, resulting in the generation of a negative open circuit voltage as shown in Fig. 7(a–b). Once the temperature gradient is established between two electrodes, the balance of the reaction is broken, leading to oxidation at the hot side and reduction at the cold side [69]. In detail, the electrochemical redox reaction of the cold electrode can be described as follows: $\text{Ni}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{3+}$ is reduced to $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Co}^{2+}$, while hydroxide ions (OH^-) are transferred to the hot electrode, where oxidation from Ni^{2+} to Ni^{3+} and Co^{2+} to Co^{3+} occurs. This leads to the generation of open circuit voltage in the TEC (Fig. S16) [71]. According to previous studies, it is significant to note that the thermal Soret effect is negligible in non-isothermal conditions, with values approximately 100 times smaller (around 10–50 $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$). Thereby, the ionic Seebeck coefficient (S_e) can be calculated from the following equation [72]:

$$S_e = \frac{\Delta V}{\Delta T} \quad (12)$$

Also, the heat energy Q_{dis} associated with the chemical reaction in the TEC can be calculated using the following equation [72]:

$$Q_{dis} = T_H \Delta S \quad (13)$$

where T_H is the working temperature of TEC and ΔS is the entropy change, equals to the summation of entropy changes at positive and negative electrodes.

The OCV of CS/ACC electrode-based H-type cell deviated from near zero value, which is indeed not an ideal thermocell, as shown in Fig. S17. In an ideal thermocell, the OCV would be zero or close to zero, since there is no net current flow and no external driving force. Therefore, the Seebeck coefficient values can only be determined for NS/ACC, and NCS/ACC electrode-based H-type cells, which are -1.8 and -2 mV K^{-1} , respectively (as shown in Fig. 7(c and d)). Also, at the high temperature gradient, NS/ACC and NCS/ACC can store up to -0.54 and -0.6 J of heat energy, which is calculated from the Eq. (13). While CoSe_2 exhibits significant deviations from the ideal OCV behaviour, the addition of NiSe_2 layer in NCS/ACC mitigated these deviations and eventually improved the Seebeck coefficient and overall efficiency of the H-type cell. The synergistic effect of Ni and Co in NCS/ACC exhibits better thermal stability compared to their pure counterparts, enabling more reliable performance under varying temperature gradients, which is crucial for ionic thermoelectric applications. These S_e values of the fabricated selenide electrodes closely align with the TC values obtained

Fig. 7. H-type non-isothermal measurement of (a and b) OCV as a function of time under different temperature gradients ($\Delta T = 0$ to 10 K), (c and d) Corresponding Seebeck voltage as a function of temperature gradients. (e and f) Effect on ΔV while applying and removing ΔT , for Symmetric H-type non-isothermal measurement based on NS/ACC and NCS/ACC electrodes, respectively.

from the isothermal configuration. This can be attributed to the selenide electrode's minimal entropy contribution when subjected to uniform temperature rise within the isothermal configuration. Subsequently, the temperature differences within the H-type cell can further lead to variations in ion distribution, ultimately resulting in a lower thermovoltage output. Other factors such as Ohmic resistance, activation and mass transport resistance can also minimise the thermovoltage [71]. Also, the previous reports suggested that the phase of the electrode material influences the entropy contribution and affects the overall thermovoltage of the system [72]. However, the NCS/ACC revealed a good Seebeck coefficient in aqueous 1 M NaOH electrolyte compared to other carbon-based electrodes in redox couple and ionic liquid electrolytes, as shown in Table S3.

From Table S3, it can be observed that carbon-based electrodes are highly preferred for heat-to-energy conversion applications because of their huge electrochemical surface area that leads to high current density under temperature gradient [73]. Also, redox couple electrolytes are mostly preferred because of their high entropy solvation and redox activity when subjected to temperature differences [74]. However, due to their toxicity in heating conditions, the current research focuses on employing sodium-based electrolytes for TEC. In this regard, the NCS/ACC-based symmetric H-type thermocell setup has revealed a promising thermovoltage of -2.3 mV K^{-1} in 1 M NaOH aqueous electrolyte. Further, Fig. 7(e–f) shows that when a temperature gradient is applied between the two electrodes, an increasing negative OCV occurs with time. Upon removal of the temperature gradient, the potential difference between the two electrodes decreases, leading to the restoration of the OCV to its initial value. The nanowire morphology and mesoporous

nature (as explained in Brunauer–Emmett–Teller analysis shown in Fig. S6) of the NCS/ACC electrodes enhances charge transfer efficiency and reaction kinetics due to its high surface area and reduced diffusion pathways. This structure fosters rapid establishment and restoration of equilibrium within the thermo-electrochemical system, thereby validating the observed reversible open-circuit voltage behaviour.

The real-time heat-to-electricity conversion of selenide electrodes was evaluated using the modified ASTM D5470-06 based setup. A sandwich-type TEC was assembled with a 1 M NaOH infiltrated Celgard separator between two symmetric selenide electrodes. A thermal gradient was generated using copper bars, with one bar connected to a heat source and the other to a Peltier cooler as shown in Fig. 6(b). The heat flow was uniform and perpendicular to the surface of the thermocell, with minimum lateral heat spreading. Four thermistors are placed inside each copper bar to measure local temperatures, allowing for the extrapolation of the temperature at the contact surface of each bar with the thermocell. The working procedures of ASTM D5470-06 system is given in Reference [75].

The OCV of the TEC was measured as a function of temperature difference between hot and cold electrodes, as shown in Fig. 8(a and b). Fig. 8(c and d) showed that the OCV of the thermocell decreased linearly with increasing temperature difference, with slopes of -2.3 mV K^{-1} and -3.4 mV K^{-1} for NS/ACC and NCS/ACC based symmetric TEC, respectively. Compared to H-type electrochemical cells, the sandwich-type TEC exhibit a significantly shorter electrode-electrode distance, which enhances thermal diffusion and a substantial increase in thermovoltage. We also calculated the thermal charge storage based on Eq. (8), where the hot electrode temperature is at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Here, the thermal charge storage increased from -0.69 and -1.02 J for NS/ACC and NCS/ACC based TECs, respectively. This is due to the reduced thermal

Fig. 8. Voltage (ΔV) as a function of time under different temperature gradients ($\Delta T = 0$ to 10 K) for (a) NS/ACC and (b) NCS/ACC based TECs. (c and d) Corresponding Seebeck voltage as a function of temperature gradients. (e and f) Effect on ΔV while applying and removing ΔT , for NS/ACC and NCS/ACC electrodes, respectively.

resistance and increased thermal conductivity between the electrodes, allowing for more efficient heat transfer and thereby increasing the Seebeck coefficient and the resulting thermovoltage [76]. Additionally, Fig. 8(e and f) shows the reversible nature of the thermocell as demonstrated by restoring the OCV by removing the thermal gradient between the electrodes. Among all the fabricated selenide electrodes, NCS/ACC has revealed an excellent electrochemical performance and is the most promising candidate for charge storage and heat-to-electricity conversion application. This enhanced performance can be attributed to the unique crystal structure of the NiSe₂-CoSe₂ composite, which synergistically combines the advantageous properties of both components [24–27]. The variation in Fermi energies between NiSe₂ and CoSe₂ generates a built-in electric field that significantly facilitates the efficient transport of ions and electrons [24–27]. Additionally, the reduced dimensions of the nanowires, along with the conductive nature of the carbon support, further enhance the overall electrochemical performance [24–27]. Future research should explore the material composition and structure of NCS/ACC electrodes to enhance electrochemical charge storage and thermoelectric performance. Integrating NCS/ACC electrodes with other energy conversion technologies, such as hybrid systems, may lead to synergistic effects and improve overall efficiency for sustainable energy solutions.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the development of NCS-ACC electrodes represents a significant enhancement in harnessing dual functionality for thermal energy conversion and electrochemical charge storage. Impressively, a synergistic combination of NiSe₂-CoSe₂ nanowires on an ACC substrate not only enhances the electrochemical charge storage properties but also maximizes operational cyclic stability. With an excellent charge storage capacity of 112 mA h g⁻¹ at a current density of 1 A g⁻¹ and a remarkable cyclic stability of 85 % capacity retention over 10,000 cycles, the NCS-ACC electrodes are well-suited for advanced charge storage applications. Concurrently, their application in TEC, utilizing a 1 M NaOH aqueous electrolyte, has demonstrated significant thermoelectric performance, achieving a Seebeck coefficient of -3.4 mV K⁻¹ and a thermal charge storage of -1.02 J under a thermal gradient of 10 K. This dual functionality not only enhances their potential as efficient charge storage materials but also showcases their capability for effective heat-to-electricity conversion. The NCS-ACC system thus emerges as a versatile candidate for innovative energy technologies, bridging the gap between electrochemical applications and thermal energy harvesting, ultimately paving the way towards integrated energy solutions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Rupa Ranjani Palanisamy: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **N. Padmanathan:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Anjali Ashokan:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Amit Tanwar:** Methodology, Investigation. **Subhajit Biswas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Justin D. Holmes:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Kafil M. Razeeb:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Kafil M. Razeeb reports financial support was provided by Tyndall National Institute. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could

have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.116568>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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